

NUMEROUS HELPFUL METHODS TO ENHANCE SPOKEN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article will help learners who will learn English and who are currently mastering English to enhance and develop the speaking skills, which is one of the 4 skills of the English language. The article also gives data about some methods to improve spoken English among learners.*

Keywords: *turn on the radio, attempt to watch the news in English, check out English-language resources, look for English-language lectures, rehearse scenarios by yourself, participate in an English play.*

For most students, speaking in a foreign language is an uphill battle. Even with straightforward speaking assignments, students frequently become disinterested, hesitate, and fail to finish them. Speaking well is regarded as a difficult skill for non-native speakers, according to research on the subject. Nonetheless, learners can improve their spoken English in a number of ways these days. Moreover, there are numerous reasons why people learn English. When planning a class or offering one-on-one instruction, it is essential to consider these elements as well as language acquisition requirements in order to ensure a successful learning experience. Probably just as important for the teacher as it is for the students. A student can more effectively plan his or her learning strategy when they have a clear understanding of why they are learning English. He or she can assist the teacher in identifying needs and desires in the classroom. When learning independently, a student can select resources based on a clearer understanding of their goals [4;67].

Let's examine two of the more popular motivations for learning English and what could be effective in reaching learning objectives. There are many benefits to learning spoken English in the modern world. English is quickly taking the lead as the universal language of many industries, including business, politics, and education. English is not only utilized in conversations between non-native speakers and native speakers, but it is also becoming more and more common in non-native speaker interactions. You can use it effectively when asked to give a lecture in English. When you need to make friends abroad, you just give it a shot in languages other than English. Proficiency in spoken English can provide you with greater access to information. For instance, going overseas to personally experience more Western customs and culture, forming friendships with foreigners through open communication in English, and taking in more classic Western plays, movies, and books, among other things [3;67].

Speaking spoken English also gives you the opportunity to socially interact with individuals from a wide range of other nations. It provides you with a window into various cultures and worldviews. You can also watch foreign movies, TV shows, listen to foreign music, and get news. Thus, in today's global village, spoken English is a crucial and essential tool [1;136].

Let's now examine some strategies for improving our oral English. So how can you get better at speaking English out loud? What steps can you take to try putting your improvement

resolution into action? Here, we will offer some specific recommendations for low- or no-cost, self-directed activities that will help you specifically get better at speaking English.

1. Turn on the radio; if you were five minutes early, you could hear the English news.
2. Attempt to watch the news in English rather than your mother tongue. Consider taping a piece of paper over the subtitles if you watch a movie with them.
3. Take your English instructor out to lunch! Find a friend who shares your desire to speak English better, and of course, have lunch or dinner together to practice speaking the language.
4. Check out English-language resources from your local library, including books, records, cassette tapes, and other items. Keep an eye out for books that feature a lot of dialogue. When you watch English-language movies, read plays instead of reading the subtitles in your home tongue.
5. Stay alert for announcements about English-language events and participate whenever you can.
6. Look for English-language lectures on subjects you are interested in. Make an effort to take notes—for yourself only.
7. Acquire the lyrics to a few well-known songs.
8. Check your local library for books on tape. If you have a walkman, listen while you are at home or on your commute.
9. Keep an eye out for English-language plays or dramatic productions on campus, or purchase a student ticket for the open shows.
10. Trade taped messages with a fellow student. After a few minutes of recording, ask a classmate to reply on the same tape at a later time.
11. Pick a well-known figure whose accent you like, and if you can find recordings of them, try mimicking their speech pattern.
12. Rehearse scenarios by yourself, maybe in front of a mirror. Imagine making an introduction, expressing disagreement with someone's viewpoints, requesting information, or being interviewed. Assign roles and engage in role-playing if you can find someone to assist.
13. Make friends with the exchange students who are on our campus; their purpose is to facilitate communication across cultural boundaries. Talk to them.
14. Participate in an English play; if you're shy, start with a small role.
15. Make some friends and decide to communicate in English at regular intervals, such as after class, dinner each day, or while taking the train home.
16. Get someone to listen to you read aloud and correct your pronunciation and intonation, or record yourself on tape and listen to your own analysis of your reading.

Establish objectives for specific areas you want to improve, such as the distinctions between words that contain the letters "f," "v," or "r," and "th." Write down the words you frequently pronounce incorrectly and practice them. Everyone is aware that language use is the only truly effective way to increase one's language proficiency. However, in actuality, we know that there are a variety of reasons why people are reluctant to speak in another language, including shyness, fear of being laughed at, difficulty expressing their true meaning, and fear of making mistakes. We've all been there at some point, but if you're serious about getting better at speaking English, give some of these tips a try. After you give some of these concepts and ideas a try, the cat will find it extremely difficult to get your tongue! [2;98].

The best strategy to get better at speaking English orally is to practice what you learn! Keep in mind that you are training your mouth to move in a new way. You are developing linguistic

muscles that are not used in your native tongue. It is comparable to working out at the gym. Remember to give your mouth a little exercise every day. To become more proficient in speaking English, we should put in more practice and give ourselves more time. Speaking English is a crucial part of learning the language. strong communication abilities as well. Competency is the ultimate aim of learning English. Right now, the emphasis is on how to improve and advance the students' spoken English ability. These methods assist the student in achieving his desired goals.

REFERENCES

1. Liu Runqing. The good language learner: survey of several factors [J]; Foreign Language Teaching and Research; 1990-02.
2. Yan Chuanhai, Zhang Meijuan; The interference of affective factors in foreign language teaching [J]; Foreign Language World;2002-05.
3. Xabarshı, Berdakh university, Press, 2020.
4. Wang Chuming; Two major factors influencing L2 learning and their effect on L2 teaching [J]; Foreign Language World; 2001-06.
5. Jumayeva, M. B. (2023). Classifications of Cardinal Numbers and Ordinal Numbers in English And Uzbek. Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnali, 3(2), 132-134.
6. Jack Challoner. Knowledge Encyclopedia Science, 2018.
7. Stuart Berg Flexner. New Oxford American Dictionary, 2001.